

Data analysis of safety incentive on unsafe behavior of construction workers based on SEM model

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Abstract

This article constructs a research hypothesis on the impact of safety incentive mechanism on unsafe behavior of construction workers with high fall risk from the perspective of safety incentives. Through literature review and analysis, 497 construction workers were selected as sample data, and empirical testing and analysis were conducted using structural equation modeling and data analysis software SPSS and AMOS. The empirical research results show that both positive rewards and negative incentives have a significant impact on unsafe behavior through the safety ability, safety attitude, and safety atmosphere of construction workers, and the model hypothesis fitting verification effect is good. The article enriches the theoretical research on the unsafe behavior of construction workers in reducing the occurrence of high fall accidents.

CCS Concepts

• **General and reference** → Document types; Surveys and overviews.

Keywords

Structural equation modeling, Safety incentives, Unsafe behavior

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1 Preface

The construction industry is characterized by labor-intensive industry and is an important pillar of China's national economy. According to statistics, there were 689 safety accidents in housing and municipal engineering production in China in 2020, of which 407 were of the high fall type, accounting for more than 50% of

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the total^[1]. During the entire construction process of the project, high-altitude operations are the most common, accounting for more than 90% of the entire construction task. High altitude falling accidents have the highest incidence rate among all types of accidents. Research has shown that the main factor behind these high fall accidents can be traced back to the unsafe behavior of construction workers^[2].

At present, scholars' research on unsafe behavior of construction workers mainly focuses on the influencing factors^[3], mechanisms^[4], and interventions^[5] of unsafe behavior. There is little research on classifying construction workers by risk and proposing constructive suggestions for preventing unsafe behavior. Research on safety incentives mainly focuses on rewards and punishments for enterprise safety production management^[6] and safety production rewards and punishments for construction project departments^[7], while there is little research on safety incentives for frontline construction workers. The above research found that safety incentives have a certain positive effect on enterprise safety management, employee safety awareness, and the ability to learn safety knowledge and skills. However, there is relatively little research on safety incentives for frontline construction workers in construction enterprises, especially those with high fall risks.

In view of this, this article takes construction workers with high fall risk as the research object, combines safety skills, safety attitudes, and safety atmosphere, uses structural equation modeling and social cognitive theory analysis to explore the impact of safety incentives on unsafe behavior of such construction workers.

2 Theoretical basis and research hypothesis

2.1 Safety incentives

Within the scope of safety, safety incentives refer to the process in which an organization takes appropriate management measures and incentive methods to motivate employees to actively engage in safety activities while consciously adhering to safety behavior norms, in order to achieve safety production management goals^[8]. Safety incentives can generally be divided into two aspects: positive incentives and negative incentives^[9]. After conducting research and literature review on incentive documents of major enterprises, this article selects four measurement indicators for positive incentives: cash rewards, point redemption, publicity and recognition, and job promotion; Select cash penalties, termination of contracts, increased assessment efforts, and criticism and education as four

measurement indicators for negative incentive. Combining the influencing factors of unsafe behavior, safety skills, safety attitude and safety atmosphere, so put forward the hypothesis: H1-H6.

2.2 Security Capability and Unsafe behavior

The safety capability of construction workers refers to the ability to identify and assess potential risks based on their own resources and environment during the construction process, in order to control personal injury and property damage to the maximum extent possible. Numerous research findings indicate that the safety capabilities of construction workers have a direct impact on unsafe behavior. In the study of management behavior by An Yu et al.^[10], improving the professional skills of construction workers is an effective way to implement construction site management behavior and reduce the possibility of unsafe behavior among workers. Liang Zhendong, Liu Haibin, and others pointed out that individual influencing factors of unsafe behavior include self-efficacy, job satisfaction, safety knowledge, and external control personality tendency^[11]. Ju Jie et al. used decision experiments and evaluation laboratory methods to divide the influencing factors of unsafe behavior into six aspects: safety skills, physical fitness, psychological resilience, and work experience^[12]. Therefore, this article selects work experience, safety knowledge, safety skills, and safety behavior habits as the four measurement indicators that affect the safety ability of unsafe behavior. And put forward the hypothesis, H7: Security capability has a significant positive impact on unsafe behavior.

2.3 Safety attitude and Unsafe behavior

The safety attitude of construction workers refers to their value judgment and emotional inclination towards the safety aspect of construction operations after evaluating the importance or significance of safety production. It is a certain idea and intention to ensure their own construction safety. Kelman HC et al. believe that safety attitude can describe and predict an individual's unsafe behavior, and even directly determine unsafe behavior^[13]. Chen Weike and Wang Bingchun explored the influence of psychological factors on unsafe behavior and found that individual cognition has a significant impact on unsafe behavior^[14]. Ju Jie et al. used decision experiments and evaluation laboratory methods to divide influencing factors into six aspects: safety attitude, safety cognition, physical fitness, and psychological fitness^[12]. Tian Shuicheng found that the psychological factors of miners are significantly related to the unsafe behaviors exhibited during the operation process, and psychological factors such as negative emotions and work attitudes have an important impact on unsafe behaviors^[15]. Therefore, this article selects safety responsibility, safety cognition, safety emotion, and safety initiative as the four measurement indicators that affect safety attitudes towards unsafe behavior. And put forward the hypothesis, H8: Safety attitude has a significant reverse effect on unsafe behavior.

2.4 Safety atmosphere and Unsafe behavior

The safety atmosphere refers to the common understanding formed by the safety subject towards the safety object, and the core of the atmosphere lies in the common pursuit of safety. Amponsah Tawaih and Adu et al. found that a safe atmosphere has a negative effect

on employee unsafe behavior^[16]. Hee Chang et al. conducted a questionnaire survey on temporary workers in the construction industry in South Korea, and established a structural equation model to demonstrate that safety culture and atmosphere have a significant impact on the occurrence of unsafe construction behaviors^[17]. Mei Yung Leung has verified that education and training, stress relief measures, and appropriate rewards are effective ways to enhance the safety behavior of construction workers^[18]. Ye Gui conducted an in-depth analysis of the variables that affect the unsafe behavior of construction workers and found that the level of attention given by leaders to safety issues plays a decisive role in reducing workers' unsafe behavior^[19]. Therefore, this article selects education and training, safety protection culture, management attention, and team communication as the four measurement indicators that affect the safety atmosphere of unsafe behavior. And put forward the hypothesis, H9: The safety atmosphere has a significant reverse effect on unsafe behavior.

2.5 Unsafe behavior

The unsafe behavior of construction workers in this article specifically refers to the unsafe behavior of construction workers in the risk of falling from heights during construction. Unsafe behavior of construction workers refers to behaviors that directly or indirectly lead to safety accidents and may trigger safety accidents on the construction site. Cao Qingren et al. proposed that fundamentally, unsafe behavior and illegal behavior are consistent, referring to violations of regulations that may cause safety accidents^[20]. Nwagbala, D. C and others believe that the unsafe behavior of construction workers is a behavior that may cause accidents, and the reason is the violation of safety operation regulations or safety rules and regulations^[21]. Therefore, this article selects five measurement indicators for unsafe behavior: illegal operations, failure to comply with safety regulations, failure to wear necessary protective gear, failure to communicate with colleagues, and failure to report hidden dangers.

3 Research hypotheses and model construction

Taking construction workers with high fall risk as the research object, the above analysis is further sorted out based on the safety incentive mechanism theory, behavior safety theory, social cognition theory and Bandura's "Triadic interaction model". This paper puts forward the following 9 assumptions:

H1: Positive incentives have a significant negative impact on safety capabilities;

H2: Positive incentives have a significant negative impact on safety attitudes;

H3: Positive incentives have a significant negative impact on the safety atmosphere;

H4: Negative incentive have a significant positive impact on safety capabilities;

H5: Negative incentive have a significant positive impact on safety attitudes;

H6: Negative incentive have a significant positive impact on the safety atmosphere;

H7: Security capability has a significant positive impact on unsafe behavior;

Figure 1: Hypothesis Mechanism Model.

H8: Safety attitude has a significant reverse effect on unsafe behavior;

H9: The safety atmosphere has a significant reverse effect on unsafe behavior;

Based on the above assumptions, the research model of this article is shown in Figure 1.

4 Empirical analysis

4.1 Questionnaire Design and Research

Based on the mechanism model of the impact of safety incentive on unsafe behavior of construction workers with high risk of falling, the questionnaire was compiled by using the 5-level scale of litek. The research objects are representative state-owned enterprises and private enterprises, and front-line construction workers from Shanghai and Sichuan projects. A total of 502 questionnaires were collected and 497 were valid, with an effective questionnaire rate of 99%.

4.2 Sample Composition

In terms of gender, men accounted for 93.6% and women accounted for 6.4%; In terms of age, construction workers aged 36-45 accounted for 32.6%, and construction workers aged 46-55 accounted for only 30.8%; In terms of education level, the proportion of construction workers with primary school education or below was 49.7%, and the proportion of construction workers with junior high school education was 31.6%; In terms of working years, the proportion of construction workers who have been engaged in the construction industry for 4-8 years is 32.8%, and the proportion of construction workers who have been engaged in the construction industry for 15 years or more is 33.0%. For the purpose of the research, the construction workers with high fall risk are to be examined, so all the sample objects are selected by the project leaders according to the actual progress of the project., indicating that the research subjects are representative.

4.3 Reliability and Validity Analysis

This article uses SPSS24.0 software to conduct reliability analysis on the variable data of the questionnaire, and the specific values are shown in Table 1. The results show that the Cronbach's α values are greater than 0.8; The load of standardization factor is greater than 0.6. The combined reliability CR values of each factor were greater than 0.7; The AVE values of all observed variables are greater than 0.5, which indicates that the logic of questionnaire item setting is reasonable. In conclusion, the scale has good reliability and convergent validity.

4.4 Model Construction and Fit Evaluation

Based on the data summarized from the questionnaire, a structural equation model of variable relationships and related path coefficients was constructed using AMOS24.0 software, as shown in Figure 2;

The software was used to test the model fitting degree, and the fitting results are shown in Table 2 the main absolute fitting indicators χ^2/df , GFI, RMSEA, and relative fitting indicators CFI, TLI, IFI required by the structural equation all meet the model fitting standards, indicating that the model has good fitting degree.

4.5 Research hypothesis testing and judgment

Whether the relationship between variables is significant is usually represented by standardized path coefficients, which are directly proportional to the correlation between variables; The validity of the research hypothesis is determined by the magnitude of the P-value, as shown in Table 3.

According to Table 3, The standardized path coefficient of positive excitation on safety capability is -0.331, $p < 0.001$, Verify H1; The standardized path coefficient of positive incentive on safety attitude is -0.472, $p < 0.001$, Verify H2; The standardized path coefficient of positive incentive on safety atmosphere is -0.387, $p < 0.001$, Verify H3; The standardized path coefficient of reverse excitation on safety capability is 0.893, $p < 0.001$, Verify H4; The standardized path coefficient of reverse incentive on safety attitude is 1.260, $p < 0.001$, Verify H5; The standardized path coefficient of reverse excitation on the

Table 1: Summary of Reliability and Validity Analysis.

Variable	Cronbach’s Alpha	AVE	CR
PI	0.913	0.737	0.918
NI	0.814	0.534	0.820
SAB	0.893	0.687	0.897
SAT	0.881	0.653	0.882
SCU	0.934	0.785	0.936
UB	0.953	0.803	0.953

Figure 2: Road-stiffness relationship of structural model.

Table 2: Model fitting index.

Fitting indicators	Adaptation standards	Inspection results	Yes/No
χ^2/df	<5	3.638	Yes
GFI	>0.80	0.865	Yes
RMSEA	<0.08	0.073	Yes
CFI	>0.90	0.926	Yes
TLI	>0.90	0.927	Yes
IFI	>0.90	0.936	Yes

Table 3: Model path coefficients and hypothesis testing results.

Posit	Path	Estimate	C.R.	P	Support
H1	PI->SAB	-0.331	-4.486	***	Yes
H2	PI->SAT	-0.472	-6.564	***	Yes
H3	PI->SCU	-0.387	-5.818	***	Yes
H4	NI->SAB	0.893	10.074	***	Yes
H5	NI->SAT	1.26	12.431	***	Yes
H6	NI->SCU	1.171	12.893	***	Yes
H7	SAB->UB	0.366	5.656	***	Yes
H8	SAT->UB	-0.38	-3.179	0.001	Yes
H9	SCU->UB	-0.101	-0.906	0.365	Yes

Note: *** indicates significance $P < 0.001$

safety atmosphere is 1.171, $p < 0.001$, Verify H6; The standardized path coefficient of full capacity for unsafe behavior is 0.366, $p < 0.001$, Verify H7; The standardized path coefficient of safety attitude to unsafe behavior is -0.380, $p < 0.001$, Verify H8; The standardized path coefficient of safety atmosphere on unsafe behavior is -0.101, $p > 0.05$, Verify that H9 is not tenable, that is, safety attitude has no significant negative impact on unsafe behavior.

Both positive and negative incentives have significant effects on unsafe behaviors of construction workers with high risk of falling, that is, safety incentives affect the final unsafe behaviors by affecting the safety ability, safety attitude and safety atmosphere of construction workers. H1-H8 of the hypotheses proposed in this article have been effectively validated.

5 Countermeasures and Suggestions

Based on this, this article proposes the following two countermeasures and suggestions:

(1) Enrich the types and channels of safety incentive mechanisms. We can broaden our thinking and practical channels, brainstorm more and adopt various incentive methods. In addition to traditional cash or material rewards, we can try to make more attempts, innovations, and combinations. For example, we can try to combine points with daily safety education for workers, and combine recognition with safety themed skill competitions to develop positive incentive mechanisms for safety. These new attempts can be gradually adjusted in specific implementation, and their implementation effectiveness can be seen from the feedback received.

(2) Emphasize the cultivation of safety capabilities and guidance on safety attitudes. Enhance the training capacity of construction workers' safety abilities, and focus on training key positions and personnel to effectively promote the growth of construction workers' safety abilities. From theoretical understanding to practical practice, everything should start from reality, strive to gain true knowledge from practice, guide attitude changes, and reduce unsafe behaviors.

(3) Establish a long-term mechanism and systematize safety education and training. Annual training plan, safety education outline, training materials, examination question bank, etc. shall be prepared; The policy stipulates that employees in high-risk industries must receive 16 hours of safety education every year to strengthen the source management of work at heights; Those who have not been trained and passed the examination are not allowed to engage in high-altitude operations. They should take safety training as their daily work and take a step forward to build a strong ideological defense line of safety production for employees.

(4) Strengthen communication and give play to the role of safety atmosphere. For example, through the establishment of the morning meeting system, adhere to the pre job disclosure, and strengthen the team management and project supervision; Communication and communication methods should be diversified. Meanwhile, multi-party research on safety incentive should be carried out in time to extract demands from the actual feedback of construction workers, such as safety incentive school and QR code security demand upload. The adopted effective demands will be rewarded to form a good safety closed-loop atmosphere.

6 Conclusion

Using the method of literature analysis and questionnaire survey, this paper determines the influencing factors of unsafe behavior of construction workers with high risk of falling from the perspective of safety incentive, constructs a structural equation model, and studies the relationship between safety ability, safety attitude, safety atmosphere and unsafe behavior from the perspective of safety incentive. Through empirical analysis, the model and data fit well, and verifies the influence mechanism of safety incentive on unsafe behavior.

The influence of safety ability, safety attitude and safety atmosphere on safety incentive and unsafe behavior is confirmed. The corresponding management suggestions and countermeasures are put forward for construction enterprises, which has certain guiding significance for promoting construction units to formulate new incentive system, standardizing construction workers' safety behavior, reducing and preventing production safety falling accidents.

References

- [1] Ministry of Housing and Urban-Rural Development of the People's Republic of China.(2022).https://www.mohurd.gov.cn/gongkai/zc/wjk/art/2022/art_17339_768565.html.
- [2] Xu,H.,Chen,Y.H., He,J.B.,Long, D.B.,Zhao,S.X. (2023).Analysis of fall accidents characteristics in building construction based on frequency statistics and χ^2 -PCC[J]. China Safety Science Journal, 33(4): 91-99.
- [3] Liu, Q. , Liang, Y. , Jiang, H. , & Gao, T. . (2023). Research on the coupled relationship of factors influencing construction workers' unsafe behaviors: a hybrid dematel-ism-micmac approach. Advances in Civil Engineering.
- [4] Ye,G.,Yue,H.Z.,Feng,X.Y., et al. (2020). Simulation study on causes of cognitive failure of construction workers' unsafe behavior. China Safety Science Journal, 30(11): 6-12.
- [5] Fang,Q.,Chen,X.C.,Daniel,C.L.,Li,C.Q. (2023).Intervention and management of construction workers' unsafe behavior: A simulation digital twin model,Advanced Engineering Informatics,Volume 58,2023,102182,ISSN 1474-0346
- [6] Krawczyk-Dembicka, E. (2017).Analysis of technology management using the example of the production enterprise from the SME sector. Procedia Engineering, 182, 359-365.11.
- [7] Zhu, J., Zhang, C., Wang, S., Yuan, J., & Li, Q. (2022). Evolutionary game analysis of construction Workers' unsafe behaviors based on incentive and punishment mechanisms. Frontiers in psychology, 13, 907382.
- [8] Meng, Q., Liu, Y., Li, Z., & Wu, C. (2021).Dynamic reward and penalty strategies of green building construction incentive: an evolutionary game theory-based analysis. Environmental Science and Pollution Research, 28, 44902-44915.
- [9] Ye, G., Yang,L.p., LI ,X.Z., et al. (2022).Study on the positive effect of rewards and punishments on the evolution of construction workers'safety behavior . Journal of Safety and Environment, 22(1) : 201-210.
- [10] ANY., Wang,H., Li,Z.Q. ,et al. (2020).Research on formation mechanism of miners' unsafe behaviors based on TPB. China Safety Science Journal, 30(10), 20.
- [11] Liang, Z. D., & Liu, H. B. (2013). SEM-based study on effects of individual characteristics factors on unsafe behavior. Zhongguo Anquan Kexue Xuebao, 23(2), 27-33.
- [12] Ju, J., Yang, G. S., & Yang, P. (2013). Study on influence factor and control measures for unsafe behavior of construction workers. J. Saf. Sci. Technol, 9(11), 179-184.
- [13] Kelman, H. C. (1974).Attitudes are alive and well and gainfully employed in the sphere of action. American psychologist, 29(5), 310.
- [14] Nwagbala, D. C. , & Park, J. Y. (2023). A study of the foremen's influence on the safety behavior of construction workers based on cognitive theory. Buildings (2075-5309), 13(7).
- [15] Tian,S.C., Kong,W.J., & Kuang, Y. (2018). Research on relationship between psychological factors of miners and their work stress response and unsafe behavior. Journal of Safety Science and Technology, 14(8), 106-111.
- [16] Amponsah-Tawaih, K., & Adu, M. A. (2016).Work pressure and safety behaviors among health workers in Ghana: the moderating role of management commitment to safety. Safety and health at work, 7(4), 340-346.
- [17] Seo, H. C., Lee, Y. S., Kim, J. J., & Jee, N. Y. (2015).Analyzing safety behaviors of temporary construction workers using structural equation modeling. Safety Science, 77, 160-168.
- [18] Leung, M. Y., Liang, Q., & Olomolaiye, P. (2016).Impact of job stressors and stress on the safety behavior and accidents of construction workers. Journal of Management in Engineering, 32(1), 04015019

- [19] Ye, G., Yang, L.J & Wang, H.X. (2019). Study on influencing factors of construction workers' unsafe behavior based on multi level hierarchical structure model. *Safety and Environmental Engineering*, 26(2), 129-134.
- [20] Cao, Q.R., Yang, X.B., Cao, M., *et al.* (2018). Impact of workers' safety participation on accidents. *China Safety Science Journal*, 28(11), 1.
- [21] Nwagbala, D. C. , & Park, J. Y. (2023). A study of the foremen's influence on the safety behavior of construction workers based on cognitive theory. *Buildings* (2075-5309), 13(7).